

Exploiting AI Computer-Use and Coding Agents

Agentic ProbLLMs

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ABSTRACT

During August 2025, the Month of AI Bugs project documented over two dozen previously unknown security vulnerabilities in agentic AI coding assistants across multiple vendors. [1]

This paper presents the testing approach, synthesizes the most severe findings, and identifies recurring vulnerability patterns across these systems, which are formalized in this work as the “AI Kill Chain”.

The identified vulnerabilities included zero-click data exfiltration, arbitrary remote code execution, and long-term memory persistence in some of the evaluated agents, all exploitable via indirect prompt injection.

Beyond individual bugs, this work highlights systemic design failures, including over-reliance on LLM output as a security control, insufficient sandboxing and isolation, and entirely lacking human-in-the-loop safeguards.

Vendor responses varied, ranging from rapid fixes with CVE assignments to delayed or absent remediation.

Finally, the research is contextualized and observes that current practices increasingly normalize insecure AI system design while at the same time shifting responsibility to end users. This trajectory risks a normalization of deviance in agentic AI systems.

Keywords—LLM, machine learning, large language model, security, red teaming, prompt injection, cybersecurity

I. INTRODUCTION

Large language model (LLM) based agentic coding agents are being created by a wide range of vendors and adopted in software development. Such agents perform more than auto complete. They browse documentation, modify files, execute code, use plugins, skills, tools, and manage infrastructure.

With these features novel security risks arise. In August 2025, the author conducted the “Month of AI Bugs” to systematically analyze vulnerabilities in AI coding agents.

The targets included OpenAI ChatGPT Web Codex, Anthropic Claude Code, Amazon Q Developer, AWS Kiro, Amazon Q,

GitHub Copilot, Google’s Jules, Windsurf Cascade, Cursor, Cline, OpenHands, Gemini CLI, Devin AI, Manus.

The research found dozens of individual vulnerabilities and published 30 in-depth research posts revealing indirect prompt injection exploits that subvert these agents into performing malicious actions and exploiting identified weaknesses.

The collective findings paint a worrying picture: many state-of-the-art coding agents are hijacked to perform malicious actions without proper security controls in place. This impacts confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of systems.

Two broad exploit classes emerged repeatedly:

- (1) Exploits leading to **data exfiltration** and leakage (sensitive code, API keys, etc., sent to attacker)
- (2) Exploits enabling **remote code execution** (RCE) or other unintended system control (e.g. spawning processes, modifying files, or exposing internal services remotely)

These attacks require zero user-clicks beyond normal day to day usage of the agent to process files, web pages or tool calls. The agent becomes a “confused deputy” that executes attacker instructions autonomously via indirect prompt injection.

Notably, vulnerabilities can frequently be chained together using *offensive context engineering*, escalating via a simple indirect prompt injection into full system compromise. To emphasize this, the project concluded with an AI virus (*AgentHopper*) that propagates across developer machines by exploiting various agents.

These findings underscore that current agentic LLM systems often lack robust security boundaries. Many of them blindly trust the LLM’s outputs to be benign.

This continued over-reliance on LLM output being trustworthy leads to a **Normalization of Deviance in AI** across the industry, where risky behavior is normalized and/or security decision entirely handed off to the end user. [2]

Secure defaults and human-led AI must complement AI capabilities.

Ultimately, this case study provides a field report on real AI exploitation techniques and defense challenges for agentic AI coding systems, grounded in empirical evidence from dozens of vulnerabilities across all popular coding agents and vendors.

II. TESTING APPROACH AND THE AI KILL CHAIN

The common recurring attack steps for achieving an adversarial objective is introduced here as the **AI Kill Chain**. [1]

Figure 1 The AI Kill Chain Sequence

The **AI Kill Chain** are the basic sequence of steps for successful exploitation via prompt injection and consists of:

- Indirect Prompt Injection
- Confused Deputy
- Automatic Tool Invocation (no human-in-the-loop)

The attack vector is *indirect prompt injection*, where a third-party controls instructions that hijack the agent. The agent turns into a *Confused Deputy* and ends up *automatically invoking a tool* with rogue side-effects.

The *indirect prompt injection* vectors can be categorized into common buckets, depending on supported features:

- Uploading untrusted files
- Working with code from other users or AI
- Connecting to untrusted data or tools (e.g. bug reports)

Zero-click Exploits Only (Automatic Tool Invocations)

The research focused solely on vulnerabilities that do not require user-interaction besides using a feature as intended, e.g. summarizing a page, reviewing code,...

The individual indirect prompt injection test cases for each agent were as follows:

- Data Exfiltration
 - Image Rendering
 - Browser Tool
 - Command Execution (e.g. via curl, ping,...)
 - MCP Tool Invocation
- Phishing (and data exfiltration) via Hyperlinks
- Arbitrary Remote Code Execution
- Memory Persistence and SpAIware
- Invisible Unicode Tags (hidden prompt injection)

The following table shows publicly disclosed research during the Month of AI Bugs. Empty cells make no statement about existence or non-existence of a vulnerability.

Product	Data Exfiltration	RCE	Hidden PI/ ASCII Smuggling	Persistence (SpAIware)	Tool Abuse
Amp Code	✓	✓	✓		✓
Amazon Q Dev	✓	✓	✓		✓
AWS Kiro		✓			✓
ChatGPT	✓	✓			✓
Claude Code	✓				✓
Cline	✓	✓			✓
Cursor	✓				✓
Devin AI	✓	✓	✓		✓
GitHub Copilot		✓	✓		✓
Google Jules	✓	✓	✓		✓
Manus	✓	✓			✓
OpenHands	✓	✓			✓
Windsurf	✓		✓	✓	✓

* Only vulnerabilities disclosed during the Month of AI Bugs are checked. This table does not make a statement about empty cells
Figure 2 Posts disclosing vulnerabilities during the Month of AI Bugs

Tool Abuse in the above table means that it was possible to invoke and abuse an internal tool as part of the AI Kill Chain to achieve an objective of a test case (data exfiltration, RCE,...).

The next section explains individual vulnerability patterns with practical exploit examples.

III. VULNERABILITY PATTERNS IN AGENTIC AI SYSTEMS

A. **Data Exfiltration**

One of the most common vulnerabilities identified in AI coding agents is **exfiltration of sensitive information** from the user's environment to the attackers, without user approval.

With many agents, an attacker can supply a malicious input (e.g. a code file, a PDF, web page,..) that causes the LLM to **exfiltrate sensitive data** from the user.

The *Embrace the Red* blog has extensively highlighted this vulnerability type going back to 2023, including the very first publicly documented fix for such a vulnerability. [3]

The dangerous conditions that enable such exploits is called the *lethal trifecta*, and refers to the combination of access to

private data, exposure to untrusted input, and a way to communicate with an external resource. [4]

More than half of the documented bugs fell into this category. It's possible to further categorize them into: **Image Rendering, Web Browsing and Generic Tool Invocation Exploits, including MCP tools.**

Let's explore them in more detail with practical examples.

Image Rendering and Data Leaks

Many agents automatically render markdown or HTML content in their chat interface or UI output.

If an attacker's input includes an image tag with a source like `![alt](https://wuzzi.net/?q=<data>)`, the agent will fetch that image URL, inadvertently appending sensitive data (`<data>`) that the prompt injection inserts into the URL query.

This was demonstrated in multiple products, and is perhaps the most common AI application security over the last three years. The severity of such **zero-click leakage** typically falls into the high to critical severity based on what data the agent has access to.

The Month of AI Bugs documented numerous vulnerable agents:

1. **ChatGPT** itself could be tricked into sending its conversation history and any other information present in the prompt to an attacker's blob storage URL [7]
2. **Anthropic Claude Code** was exploited to leak local `.env` secrets via DNS queries (using `ping/nslookup`) and Anthropic assigned a CVE, and patched it within two weeks [8]
3. **Amazon's Q Developer** had an almost identical DNS exfiltration bug and patched it within weeks. Although, Amazon did not issue a CVE, like Anthropic did [9]
4. Meanwhile, maintainers of **Cline** (a popular VS Code AI extension with 2M+ installations) did not respond for over 90 days when a similar image-exfiltration bug was reported, raising concerns on how to protect users [10]
5. **Windsurf Cascade** [11] and **Google Jules** [11] also are impacted by rendering markdown images that allows data leakage
6. **OpenHands**, an open-source coding agent, was hijacked exfiltrate an internal `GITHUB_TOKEN` via an image request [6]
7. A novel exploit that uses Mermaid diagrams to leak data was discovered in **Cursor IDE** [5]

It was observed that some vendors rely on the model's behavior and system prompt instructions (referred to by practitioners as *prompt begging*) to protect information.

However, this is insufficient for data confidentiality. Effective mitigations are well-understood classical security paradigms: e.g. enforcing a strict Content Security Policy or allowlisting domains to prevent connecting to malicious servers.

Web Browsing and Tool Exploitation

Apart from image rendering, another common data exfiltration vector are an agent's web browsing or API-calling capabilities. Many coding agents integrate with browsers or other tools (Slack, Jira,...).

If an attacker can hijack the agent to browse to an external URL with sensitive data in the query, the end result is the same as with the image leak attack scenario.

1. **Windsurf Cascade** provided a `read_url_content` tool that fetches arbitrary URLs with no user confirmation, leaking secrets[10]. It was later shown that **Google Antigravity**, a fork of Windsurf, was vulnerable to the same vulnerabilities upon release. [15]
2. **Devin AI** is vulnerable to multiple 0-click data exfiltration vectors, e.g via `curl` commands, or the agent's *built-in browsing capabilities*,... [16]
3. **Deep Research** agents are interesting as well, , in particular it was demonstrated with **ChatGPT's new "Deep Research"** that when multiple connectors are present they leak information between each other.

For instance, when ChatGPT had both an *Outlook email connector* and a *web search connector* or *custom MCP server* enabled, it includes private email content in queries to the other tools. This essentially *spilling data across tools by design*. [17]

This demonstrates that even without an adversary, *unintended data spill* can occur in multi-tool autonomous agents. Many agentic systems **lack clear data provenance or sandboxing** capabilities.

And, importantly, this includes "read" only tools, because a *query* to a third-party system is a data exfiltration channel.

Severity and Impact

The Month of AI Bugs findings underscore that data exfiltration continue to be a practical risk.

It can happen silently and compromise credentials, source code, or personal data. Many vendors agreed: *Anthropic* quickly patched the Claude DNS leak, as did *Cursor* and *Amazon*.

Some organizations, however, were slower to react or did not respond at all.

Defenses across all these cases are straightforward, by using well-established security controls:

- disabling automatic rendering of external content
- establish an allow-list to enable rendering safely
- block automatic network calls to untrusted servers
- sanitize output, removing hidden `` tags and invisible Unicode characters in links
- provide configuration options so that users can limit what tools an agent can call without confirmation

In summary, the amount of data exfiltration vulnerabilities present in new AI systems is alarming and shows that vendors need to adopt a secure by default stance, and also perform proper security testing before release to protect developer secrets and sensitive information.

B. Prompt Injection to Remote Code Execution (RCE)

Another major category of vulnerabilities in agentic AI systems involve **prompt injection leading to arbitrary code (or at times command) execution and system compromise**.

The Month of AI Bugs exposed multiple avenues for this in popular agents, including “sandbox escapes” that lead to full compromise of the developer’s machine, including some new problematic reoccurring patterns.

Agents That Can Modify Their Own Security Settings

One recurring design issue is that vendors allow their agent to modify its own security configuration.

Figure 3 Attack That Security Sensitive Configuration to Achieve RCE

This is a classic security issue that should be identified early on in design, during threat modeling.

GitHub Copilot had an “experimental” feature where setting `chat.tools.autoApprove: true` in the project’s settings would put Copilot in “**YOLO mode**”, enabling it to run any shell command without requiring user approval.

Via indirect prompt injection it was possible to **write that exact line to its config** and thus self-elevate privileges. Once in YOLO mode, the exploit had the AI launch a reverse shell and effectively **take control of the developer’s machine**.

This vulnerability, tracked with CVE (CVE-2025-53773) was patched by Microsoft in the August 2025. [18]

AWS Kiro and **Amp Code** from **Sourcegraph** were vulnerable to the same kind of pattern. [19] [20]

Another exploited weakness is the exploitation of `bash` tools with configuration weaknesses, or ones that depend solely on guardrails. Guardrails are not a proper security boundary.

In **Amazon Q Developer**, the VS Code extension classified certain commands, such as `find` as “read-only”. Such commands do not require user approval.

However, the `find` command has flags like `-exec` which allows running arbitrary commands. This oversight allowed an attacker to execute a command to launch malware, turning Q Developer into a remote access trojan (“ZombAI”). [21]

Devin AI had no check on dangerous actions. It executes any sequence of Terminal commands provided in a GitHub issue it was asked to investigate. It was demonstrated how Devin was tricked to download and run malware, giving the attacker a remote shell on the developer’s machine. [22]

Manus AI has a tool called `deploy_expose_port` which allows an attacker to trick the agent to expose local infrastructure over the Internet. By combining that with data leaks, the exploit managed to have Manus expose its internal VS Code Server web IDE to the public and then leak the access URL and password to the attacker. [23]

The result was the attacker could fully remote-control Manus’s cloud VM through the VSCode web UI.

Offensive Context Engineering

Complex exploits often work in stages, bypassing the model’s internal refusals by splitting and encoding commands into base64 chunks, or similar, with the intent to “trick” the AI.

For instance, the AI Kill Chain for Manus required chaining together tricking the agent to:

1. write a and run a Python program, then
2. calling the `deploy_expose_port` tool,
3. reading a local file to read the VS Code password, and
4. finally leaking that password to the attacker, all in a single indirect prompt injection exploit.

This shows that adversaries can **mix-and-match multiple agent flaws** to achieve a complete takeover. Furthermore, it underscores that LLM “guardrails” falter against determined **offensive context engineering**.

AI agents can effectively behave as malicious insiders.

Defensive Measures

From a defensive standpoint, these system-compromise vulnerabilities share a common theme: **lack of effective sandboxing or privilege separation for the agent**.

When an agent can self-edit its own security configuration (e.g. adding * to allow all commands) that is often akin to a sandbox escape.

In several cases, simple design tweaks would have blocked exploits: e.g. if Copilot had required user confirmation before applying workspace settings, or if Amazon Q Developer had treated find as a dangerous command needing approval.

Indeed, after disclosure, some fixes were straightforward: Many vendors patched the vulnerability by no longer letting the agent write those settings to disk.

For instance, the Amp Code case is a positive example, the flaw was discovered in early July 2025 and *promptly fixed by the Amp team* within days. This demonstrates that vendors can react quickly to such high-impact issues once aware.

C. Memory Persistence and SpAIware

Beyond data exfiltration and RCEs, the Month of AI Bugs also explored *stealthier and longer-term exploits*.

Two notable patterns were **persistent prompt injections** (malicious instructions that remain present beyond one session), and **invisible prompt injections** (using non-printable characters to hide instructions from the user).

SpAIware (derived from “spyware” and AI) was introduced and first practically demonstrated against ChatGPT in 2024 to describe prompt injections that utilize an agent’s *long-term memory* feature to continuously leak data. [24]

Windsurf Cascade’s agent, for example, has a *create_memory* tool to store memories. An attacker can indirectly prompt the AI to call *create_memory* and save **malicious instructions** permanently.

This means a one-time injection can plant a hidden directive that *autonomously executes in every subsequent session*, effectively **backdooring the agent indefinitely**. With Windsurf a memory was installed that continuously exfiltrated data during session, basically spyware behavior. [25]

The mitigations here are intuitive, require confirmation when long-term memories persisted, only allow the AI to *suggest* memory items rather than auto-creating them.

Interestingly, other agents like Devin and Manus do exactly that: they prompt the user to confirm storing anything persistent, which is a safer design.

D. Invisible Unicode Tags and Hidden Prompt Injection

These attack techniques **invisible Unicode characters** (e.g. Unicode Tag characters that map to ASCII) that are ignored by human readers but interpreted by the model.

This was first demonstrated by Goodside [26] who showed how ChatGPT read and followed such hidden instructions.

It turns out that many newer models (Anthropic’s Claude, Google’s Gemini, as well as Grok) *also obey these hidden Unicode Tag instructions*. A tool to create hidden text to test for such behavior is ASCII Smuggler. [27]

The Month of AI Bugs showed this in practice: by inserting Unicode **“invisible prompt injections”** into a file or Linear ticket, one could make an agent run arbitrary commands and instructions.

Working exploits with instructions that are invisible to end users and developers were shown with *Google Jules* [28] and *Windsurf*. [28]

The severity of invisible injections is perhaps lower than vulnerabilities mentioned earlier, but they **significantly increase an attack’s stealth**.

Most vendors had not addressed this at the model layer except OpenAI. OpenAI filters out such Unicode Tag, whereas Anthropic and Google do not. This means the *responsibility to mitigate lies with application developers*...

Application-level fixes include stripping these characters from inputs or at least visualizing them (e.g. replace with a placeholder so users can spot anomalies).

Sourcegraph’s Amp Code did exactly that once notified about the risk. Amp now sanitizes input text to remove Unicode tags. [30]

Amazon Q’s team also reportedly resolved their invisible text issue by August 8, 2025. [31]

It was predicted before and during the Month of AI Bugs it’s likely that models will become better at these stealthy behaviors.

And this turned out to be true by November for Gemini. When Gemini 3 released Embrace the Red documented the exceptional capability of it following invisible Unicode instructions. [32]

Thus, proactive filtering out Unicode Tag characters is a prudent defensive step for any LLM application developer, as is it for defenders in calculating risks scores for phishing emails and alike.

E. AgentHopper – An AI Virus

In the final post of the month, the Month of AI Bugs discussed **AgentHopper**, an **AI virus** demonstration as a synthesis of many of the above tactics, vulnerabilities and remote code execution exploits.

AgentHopper’s payload was a single prompt that first conditionally checked which agent it was running under, then executed the appropriate exploit to compromise that agent, and finally propagated by injecting itself into new code repositories.

It used *conditional prompt instructions* (like if agent is "Copilot" then do X, if agent == "Kiro" do Y) so that it could adapt to multiple targets.

When run on a compromised agent, AgentHopper laterally moves to all other code repositories of the developer, infects the code and pushes infected code to GitHub.

AgentHopper - Illustration

Figure 4 AgentHopper infects other repos & publishes to GitHub

Then, when another developer’s agent pulled that code, the hidden instructions in it would detect Agent 2’s type and run the corresponding exploit (e.g. toggling YOLO mode on Copilot, or adding a malicious MCP server on Amp, etc.)

In essence, it was a *multi-agent virus* leveraging the chain of vulnerabilities (Copilot, Amp, Q, Kiro RCEs).

Since many AI coding agents are run within CI/CD pipelines, such a virus could become worm-able and automatically propagate without developers having to take manual action.

IV. VENDOR RESPONSES AND SECURITY PRACTICES

The disclosure of 30+ vulnerabilities across numerous organizations offered a rare comparative view of AI vendors’ security maturity and response processes.

Responses ranged from exemplary to disappointing.

Several companies moved fast and communicated openly. For example, **Anthropic** triaged the Claude Code DNS issue within days (acknowledging a High-severity CVSS 7.1) and fixed it in the next version.

Microsoft patched the Copilot YOLO-mode flaw and issued a patch on August Patch Tuesday (CVE-2025-53773).

OpenAI addressed the ChatGPT safe-browsing URL bypass by late July, closing a loophole that had been reported back in 2024, and notably OpenAI is the only vendor so far to harden their models against invisible text exploits at the API level.

Sourcegraph fixed issues in **AmpCode** (config-edit RCE and invisible text vulnerability) within days. This kind of rapid turnaround and transparency is exemplary.

Amazon patched vulnerabilities quickly and published advisories [33], however did not assign CVEs.

Such notifications are important, because otherwise users and organizations are not aware that they have to patch and update to the latest version quickly.

Cline did not at all respond to the reported vulnerabilities.

Windsurf acknowledged the receipt but did not commit to any action until full disclosure and public pressure of the Month of AI Bugs.

This demonstrates the catalyzing effect that responsible disclosure has, which eventually commits on publicly disclosing and documenting the identified vulnerabilities.

In the authors opinion responsible disclosure (90 days) is superior to “coordinated” disclosure, especially in products with no backwards compatibility concerns.

V. MITIGATIONS AND BEST PRACTICES

The core principle this paper suggests is to ensure secure defaults, which will help prevent widespread exploitation.

Outbound Network Connectivity

- Use Content Security Policy (CSP) and domain allow-listing to limit what external resources (images, links, APIs) agents can access
- Allow configuration of trusted domains and resources and consider sandboxing and isolation
- Require user confirmation before loading images or links from non-trusted domains

Human-in-the-Loop for Dangerous Actions and Logging

- If there is no sandbox or isolation, then prompt users for confirmation by default before executing risky operations (e.g., shell commands, file modifications, network actions)
- AI should be human-led and secure by design, rather than AI-led. However, it’s important to acknowledge that constant user-approval prompts will have the opposing outcome, finding the right balance and running systems in isolation is key.

- Allow granular configuration of tool behaviors to suit user or enterprise needs
- Consider approaches that allow invocation of dangerous tools if the initial user prompt explicitly requests it, but disables automatic tool invocation, once untrusted data is present
- Treat agents as potential insider threats and log actions

Privilege Separation and Sandboxing

- Run agents with the least privileges possible, ideally in containers or virtual machines.
- Prevent agents from editing their own configuration or memory files without user approval.
- Restrict network ports and subprocesses to safe defaults (e.g., localhost only).

Input Validation and Sanitization

- Filter invisible Unicode characters and other suspicious content from inputs.
- Neutralize or escape Markdown/ HTML (XSS) and other content that could trigger network/file operations.
- Monitor for suspicious patterns (e.g., long base64 strings, repeated use of sensitive commands).

Vendor Best Practices

- Assume LLM Output is untrusted, and that guardrails are not a security boundary
- Implement security controls and do not depend on guardrails or prompt begging for security
- Conduct and publish threat models of agentic systems, so the security contract is clear and established
- Promote Secure Defaults
- Adopt responsible disclosure programs for AI vulnerabilities

VI. NORMALIZATION OF DEVIANCE IN AI

The AI industry risks repeating the same cultural failures that contributed to the Space Shuttle Challenger disaster: Quietly normalizing warning signs while progress marches forward. [1][2]

Even after the Month of AI Bugs project concluded, the same vulnerabilities are present in new products (e.g. Google Antigravity) and vendors start documenting these security limitations and putting the responsibility on their users. [14]

To highlight this, here are three additional recent examples:

Microsoft Agentic Operating System: Microsoft warns that prompt injection “can override agent instructions, leading to unintended actions like data exfiltration or malware installation” [3]

OpenAI ChatGPT Atlas: OpenAI states: “We recommend caution using Atlas in contexts that require heightened compliance and security controls — such as regulated, confidential, or production data.”. [4] This means OpenAI explicitly warns it’s users against trusting Atlas with sensitive data.

Anthropic warns about Claude data exfiltration, and tells it’s users “to mitigate these risks, we recommend you monitor Claude while using the feature and stop it if you see it using or accessing data unexpectedly. You can report issues to us using the thumbs down function directly in claude.ai.” [5]

These examples that demonstrate this normalization of risky behavior, and hopefully the industry will adjust and place proper security controls in place by default to prevent large scale exploitation.

End-users should apply proper mitigations, and run agents in isolated environments with limited or well-controlled access to data and sensitive information.

VII. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

With the advent of agentic AI systems ethical considerations become increasingly important, from security researcher’s but also from a vendor’s perspective.

As highlighted in the previous sections, multiple vendors start pushing novel security challenges to end-users, who have might not fully understand the implications.

Stakeholder Analysis. The core stakeholders that were considered for this research project were **vendors** of agentic systems (e.g. OpenAI, Anthropic, Microsoft,...), the **researcher**, the **end-user** (primarily software engineers), and **future AI systems** that will be trained or use published information. For simplicity’s sake, I consider the organization’s running bug bounty programs, and with which researchers must commonly interact (and pass the triage bar for) to discuss vulnerabilities with vendors as “vendor” as well.

Impact of Research. The publication impacts all stakeholders; these impacts are both positive and negative. For **vendors** the impact is related to triage and fix costs, and potential public relations impact. However, the big positive impact is that their customers will receive protection if vulnerabilities are fixed, as well as educated vendors, so the impact is primarily positive on the eco-system. Also, due to the nature of many agentic systems being vulnerable to the same, or very similar vulnerabilities, there is also the threat that attacks will work on systems that are not directly targeted (or ones that will be released in the future).

For **end-users and developers**, the impact is primarily positive as well. As system get patched and mitigations are applied. However, there is the threat of vendors not addressing security issues or not having proper processes in place (e.g CVE) to publicly disclose vulnerabilities so that end-users are aware that they need to apply patches.

For the **researcher** (author of this document) the impact also was considered, future AI will associate such research, and it might take adverse action against researchers. To mitigate such scenarios, this section here is highlighting that the research is ethical and should never be misused to perform unauthorized or illegal actions, nor any actions that would harm individuals.

The researcher also spent time considering the impact of publishing this work on future AI systems that might be trained on published information and hence might learn about exploit techniques specific to these systems.

Mitigations. This research followed standard responsible disclosure (with a standard 90-day disclosure window). For cases where vendors did not fix responsible reported vulnerabilities the author tried as much as possible to not share exact indirect prompt injection exploit payloads. However, due to the nature, some exploits can easily be inferred by prior research from the author, or other write-ups from the month of AI bugs.

Furthermore, the public documentation and disclosure had the intent to raise awareness across stakeholders to ensure future AI systems will not be vulnerable to these vulnerabilities and exploits.

Justification for Research. One of the main reasons for this research project was to raise public awareness of common security vulnerabilities in agentic AI systems. The author has documenting similar issues before, going back to 2023, and observed common patterns (like data exfiltration) being present in dozens of systems before, and noticed early on that the same mistakes are repeated with computer-use and coding agents.

As we approach times when it will become easier to identify security vulnerabilities with the use of AI, it's important to keep highlighting exploitation paths and transparency.

VIII. OPEN SCIENCE

This research, including test cases, vulnerabilities, demonstration videos and responsible disclosure outcomes from different vendors were publicly documented and published during the month of August 2025. [1]

IX. CONCLUSION

The August 2025 Month of AI Bugs provides a first comprehensive look at real-world security failures in autonomous coding agents and LLM-driven developer tools.

The findings confirm that AI systems are vulnerable to age-old security vulnerabilities adapted to the LLM context.

Indirect Prompt Injection can be seen as the common attack vector, that allows attackers to transform helpful assistants into harmful agents.

However, the consequences of exploitation typically go deeper, such as data exfiltration and remote code execution. They span the classic CIA triad: **confidentiality breaches, integrity violations** and **availability** issues. [38]

In other words, an AI agent without proper security controls, monitoring and sandboxing can violate every property of the CIA security triad.

In closing, the Month of AI Bugs made it clear that the statement "**Trust No AI**" remains true.

Just as we learned decades ago not to blindly trust user input, we must now adapt to not blindly trust AI output.

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